

Current Education System in India-A Holistic Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Education in every sense is one of the essential factors of development. No country can achieve sustainable economic development without substantial investment in human capital. It is undeniable that education enriches people's understanding of themselves and of the world. The concept of Education is dynamic. It has passed through many ages and stages evolution and at every stage it has had a different meaning according to the existing social condition. Historically Naturalism as a philosophy of Education developed in the 19th century. The democracy enshrined in our constitution. In those days education syllabus were Vedas, Brahmins, Upanishads and Dharmasutras. So modern education begins in India under the British rule. Perhaps India needs independent and uniformed curriculum. Centralized education system may help every student to receive psychologically supportive and well balanced education for their bright future. Education with holistic perspective is concerned with the improvement of every student's intellectual, emotional, physical, social, artistic creative and spiritual potentials. It focuses only on curriculum of school education in general and impact of information Technology in particular.

Keywords: Education, Student, Spiritual potential, Modern education, Philosophy

Introduction

To envisage the future, it is crucial to examine the educational programs implemented throughout the British era. The requirements of the colonial powers had an impact on the development of the educational system during the British era. The British designed the school system to achieve their objectives. People can be empowered in all facets of their lives through education. His worldview, skill set, and knowledge are all widened by it. Additionally, it aids in fostering moral and ethical principles. In addition to all of this, the increased career prospects and potential for higher income go hand in hand.¹

The actual educational systems in place have a significant impact on an economy's prosperity. In today's world, education is the foundation of every system and civilized society. Considering the value of a good education, a developed nation is also an educated nation.²

Research Methodology

An overview of studies on the issues with the Indian educational system led to the creation of this research output. The study's primary focus is on description. For the purposes of the study, secondary data are utilized.

The Educational Systems in India during in the British Period

A significant turning point in British India's educational history is the Charter Act of 1813. The earliest legislative acknowledgement of the right to education in India as a function of public funds was made in Section 43 of the Charter Act of 1813. Ten years prior to Lord Macaulay's arrival in India, in 1823, the General Committee of Public Instruction was founded. The Committee's principal objective was to provide the company with educational advice. The group was controlled by Orientalists, who supported promoting Oriental education over Anglican education. Orientalist members made up the Committee of Public Instruction until 1824. As a result, the committee's homogeneous nature was lost when new members were added. The disagreement regarding the conflicting goals of eastern and western learning first surfaced in 1835. The extension of education in India wasn't completed until 1835 due

to the controversy between Orientalists and Anglophiles. The Charter ultimately received a 20-year extension in 1833. Although it did add a member of the law to the Executive Council of the Governor General of Bengal, which had just three members before, it did not contain any explicit educational qualifications. The first Law Member to be nominated, Macaulay, left for India in 1834. This resulted in a significant change in Indian educational policy throughout history.

The British education strategy was depicted in Macaulay's Resolution in a reasonably clear manner. According to Macaulay, the goal of increasing scientific literacy could only be achieved by using English as the primary language of instruction. The arguments made against English by Arabic and Sanskrit was rejected by Macaulay. Because English was the language supported by the ruling elite, he believed that it held the secret to modern knowledge. His Minute also declared that the primary goal of the British government was to introduce Indians to European literature and science, and that all funding for education would be used for that purpose through the use of the English language. The strategy, medium, means, and goals of education in India were finally defined by the then-Governor-in-General's Minute because he loved the English language. Soldier and statesman Lord William Bentinck was from the United Kingdom. From 1828 until 1835, he presided as the Governor-General of India. "I give entire concurrence to the sentiments expressed in the Minute," he wrote in one line beneath his signature to demonstrate his support for the Minute. He signed the March 1835 Resolution, which represented the first official British government position on education in India. The purpose, substance, and delivery methods of education in India were ultimately established by the Resolution of March 1835. The British rule in India made it clear that they sought to advance Western science and art.³ The following changes in Indian education were directly a result of Bentinck's declaration.

- The British set the educational objectives in India.
- The stated purpose was understood to be the advancement of Western arts and sciences.
- The publication of Asian works was to come to an end.

- Future subsidies or stipends for students attending oriental colleges were to be halted.
- English would be used as the educational language.

Making higher classes blind supporters of the government, according to the British rulers, is essential to maintaining British dominance in India in peace at the beginning of the 19th century. They sought to accomplish this through teaching the upper classes.

- The British kings required educated workers to manage the government and business.
- The Government did not receive enough funding for mass education.
- English-medium educated individuals would typically hold higher positions in the government and, in exchange, utilize their clout to prevent the general populace from rebelling against governmental authority.
- The British Parliament was required to examine the East India Company Charter Act in 1853. A Special Parliamentary Committee was constituted by the British Parliament to offer recommendations on the ideal educational strategy for India. According to The Despatch's mission statement, the school's goal was "not only to produce a higher degree of intellectual fitness, but to raise the moral character and to supply with servants." One of the main objectives of education was to spread knowledge of Europe, especially its philosophy, science, and literature.

The Wood's Dispatch of 1854 marked the end of schooling under the East India Company, which ceased to be a significant political entity in 1858. As a result of this event, Calcutta became the center of emphasis for education instead of London, and parliamentary interest in Indian education barely decreased. When it comes to solving significant issues in education, the Indian government has proven to be the most successful institution.³

The Dispatch of 1854 and the Report of the Indian Education Commission, both of which were published in 1882, served as the foundation for the educational

policies that were in place from 1854 and 1902. There are many reasons why the Commission was created. According to a Government of India Resolution from February 3, 1882, Lord Ripon assigned the Indian Education Commission to manage this responsibility. William Hunter, a member of Victoria's Legislative Council, presided over the commission. The State's efforts in the sectors of the educational system covered by its provisions, additions, and improvements may be more fully realized than previously.

In accordance with the Indian Education Commission's (1882–1833) proposal, the government gave substantial thought to how to advance basic education as well as technical education at the high school level. When Lord Curzon served as Viceroy of India from 1882–1883 to 1901–1902, the advancement of education was examined.⁴

Lord Curzon's Educational Policy

There were 150 resolutions approved during the Lord Curzon-organized Simla Educational Conference, which addressed just about every facet of education. On January 27, 1902, a Commission was appointed, and Sir Thomas Releigh served as its chairman.

- The purpose of schooling was to obtain a government position.
- Technical education was neglected, and the study of English was promoted at the expense of regional languages.
- The way students were taught promoted memorization rather than intellectual growth.

The Aftermath of Lord Curzon's Education Policy

With the Simla conference in September 1901, a period of escalating educational activity and serious pursuit of educational reforms began. The group was created in 1902, and its recommendations resulted in the Indian Universities Act being passed in 1904. The announcement of the Educational Policy, which was enacted by a government decree in 1913, was the next significant turning point. In addition to these modifications, non-officials like Gopala Krishna Gokhale pushed for a Bill to make

kindergarten through third grade free and required. Over a 20-year span, each of these developments significantly aided in the advancement of education.

The Indian Universities Act was passed in 1904 based on the recommendations of the Commission of 1902. G.K. Gokhale advocated for a policy that would make elementary education for kids between the ages of 6 and 10 both free and required. Until the addition of elementary and secondary schools in 1906, the educational institutions were divided into lower primary and higher primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary. The choices made by Gokhale and the groups that supported him had a big impact in the decades that followed. His initiatives strengthened the argument for public education and led to the establishment of a separate department of education.

The Gopal Krishna Gokhale's Bill was rejected by the British government because of a lack of funding, and the idea of compulsory education was also rejected.

- The basic and high school courses should be made more useful and practical.
- There should be higher education facilities in India so that Indian kids won't have to study abroad.
- Their standards should be upgraded rather than the quantity of already existing institutions being increased.

Upper primary schools should be opened concurrently with the expansion of lower primary schools, according to the Government Resolution on Educational Policy (1913). It recommended streamlining monitoring and inspection, hiring qualified teachers, funding Maktabas and Pathshalas, modernizing school facilities, and boosting girl education. It also recommended subsidizing Maktabas and Pathshalas.

The Government of India established the Calcutta University Commission in 1917 to assess the standing and potential of Calcutta University, and Dr. Michael Sadler served as its vice chancellor. The matriculation examination was administered by the institutions to mark the end of the school stage and served as a test for entrance

to universities. Universities also provided the Intermediate Examination, another open test, after two years.⁵

It is advised that first-degree undergrad courses last three years and include honors-level curriculum. A Board of Secondary and Intermediate Education should be established in order to organize high school and intermediate education along its recommended lines and to hold the matriculation and intermediate exams. Some of the essential components that the Sadler Commission earlier acknowledged in its conclusions are still there when we examine the educational scene in India now. An important turning point in India's educational reforms was the implementation of the 10+2+3 New Pattern of Education in 1975. Remember that the Sadler Commission (1917–1919) suggested a three-year degree program and 12 years of study. The Sadler Commission can be seen as a forerunner of the current national education system in this way. Establishing dyarchy, or dual rule, in the provinces was the primary goal of the rule of India Act of 1919. The Ministers, who were Indians, were in charge of "Transferred subjects," while the Councillors, who were British, were in control of "Reserved subjects." In India, the ministers took up direct responsibility for education, a transferred concern.

Central advisory board of Education 1921

The Central Advisory Board of Education was established at the center in 1921 as a result of the requirement for a body to manage educational matters. The concept of a national advisory board for education was first put forth by the Calcutta University Commission (1917–19). It was expected of the Indian government to "perform an invaluable function by defining the general objectives of educational policy, by providing advice and assistance to local governments and universities, and by supplying organized information regarding the development of educational ideas in the various provinces, as well as elsewhere other than in India." The Board's major responsibility was to offer wise advice on important educational issues that were brought before it. The group included renowned educationists from the provinces who were both official and non-official, and its chairman was the government of India's educational commissioner. The Board served as a forum where complex issues could

be brought for discussion and would have actually assisted Ministers in developing a strategy that would improve India.

The Board was disbanded in 1923 as part of a retrenchment plan to save a total of just a few thousand rupees in recurring expenses. The justification for its upkeep was not even discussed with the provincial administrations. Another flaw in the retrenchment plan was the union of the Indian government's revenue and agriculture departments with the departments of education and health. The departments of education, health, and land were transferred to the single department. The restrictions of such a badly managed economy led to the C.A.B.E.'s reinstatement in 1935, in accordance with the Hartog Committee's 1929 recommendations. The Board reconvened for the first time on December 19 and 20, 1935, in New Delhi. On the C.A.B.E.'s advice, the Bureau of Education was likewise restored in 1937. In 1945, it underwent additional reinforcing and reconstruction.

The Hartog Committee, 1929

The provinces were given a large level of power by the Government of India Act of 1919. For enhancing both general and professional education, Sir Philip Hartog offered a number of thorough proposals. Its final report was submitted by the committee in September 1929. The Committee then considered secondary and higher education. They were thought to have been developed in order to produce competent officials. The key finding of the study was that raising educational standards and lowering quality always went hand in hand. During the latter two decades of its control in India, the British government's educational priorities were significantly influenced by the Hartog Committee Report.

All educational activities were divided exclusively into the two categories of federal (central) and state (provincial) under the Government of India Act, which was adopted by the British Parliament in 1935. All education-related matters of all other categories save those on the federal list were governed by state or provincial laws. Additionally, the Executive, which answered to the Legislature, took full control of the Provinces' administration. Popular Ministers were given authority over things pertaining to their provinces. In a nutshell, the entire area of provincial administration

was turned over to a ministry. In 1937, the Provincial Autonomy system of administration was introduced.

Seven provinces of British India were taken over by the Congress party. The provincial ministers spent a lot of their brief tenure in office thinking about education. They made an effort to take a more comprehensive view of Indian education (Kochhar). One of the province government's riskier attempts was the Wardha Scheme. The main idea of the program was "Learning through Activity." The details of the plan were drafted by the Zakir Hossain Committee, which also produced extensive curricula for a number of trades. It was emphasized in the Abbot-Wood Report (1936–1937) that vocational students needed to receive a good general education and that general education and vocational education were not fundamentally two different fields of study.

But the Second World War broke out in 1939, and Congress ministers left in 1940, so the plan was shelved. Several committees were formed at this period by the Central and Provincial Governments to investigate various facets of Indian education.

Due to the lack of popular ministers, the prominence of Indian political issues, and the government's attention on war-related responsibilities, educational advancement stalled between 1940 and 1946. A comprehensive research on the "Post-War Educational Development in India" following the Second World War was published by the Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) in India. This was the first in-depth examination of the issues with education in the country. It is occasionally referred to as the Sargent Plan in honor of John Sargent, who at the time served as the Government of India's educational advisor. The plan's goal was to bring the level of academic brilliance that had previously been recognized in England to India over a minimum of forty years. Remember that the British Government put forth this idea in an effort to obstruct efforts by leaders of the liberation movement to establish a National System of Education akin to the Wardha Scheme.

- Pre-primary education is universally available and required for children aged 3-6.

- High schools to be of two types: academic and technical and vocational. Elementary education for the age range of 6 to 11 years. High school education for the age group of 11 to 17 years. With various curriculum, adequate technical, commercial, and artistic education.
- Demise of the intermediate course.
- In 20 years, adult education will advance and adult illiteracy will be eliminated.
- emphasis on teacher education, physical education, and education for those with physical and mental disabilities.⁶

Progress of Education after Independence

The expansion of facilities for the elementary education that is universally mandated, the reform of the secondary and university educational systems, the growth of vocational and technical education at various levels, the promotion of women's education, and the restructuring of the administrative structure of educational institutions are some of the most challenging issues in the field of education that the national government must address.

It became necessary for a number of committees and commissions to look into educational issues and offer recommendations in order to adapt education to the changing demands, goals, structure, and strategy. In order to guarantee liberty, justice, and equality as well as free public education at the time, India needed a strong constitution. The following five features of Indian education are listed in numerous sections of the constitution that deal with education in the republic:

- According to Article 45 of the Indian Constitution, the State shall use all reasonable efforts to ensure that all children get free and mandatory primary education within 10 years of the commencement of this Constitution, continuing till the age of fourteen.
- The Indian Constitution's Articles 28(1), 28(2), 28(3), and 30 safeguard secular education from religious teaching. In India, which is a secular country, each faith is free to preach its own religious ideas.

- According to Articles 29 and 30 of the Constitution, minorities in India are given unique cultural and educational rights, including the freedom to create and run educational institutions based on their preferred religion or language. This procedure is known as "Equality of Opportunity in Educational Institutions."
- The Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, as well as other socially and educationally disadvantaged segments of the Indian community, are protected under Articles 15, 17, and 46 of the Indian Constitution.
- Languages and Educational Safeguard: Under Article 29(1), any group of citizens who live on Indian territory or a portion of it and have a distinctive language, script, or culture are free to interpret this clause as they see proper.

Under the direction of Dr. S. Radha Krishnan, the Government of India established the University Education Commission in 1948, and its final report was delivered in 1949.

The Central and State Governments have been working to give the initiatives outlined in the Five-Year Plans a concrete form in an effort to accomplish all of these goals. The aims and objectives of higher education in Independent India experienced a significant change with the establishment of the University Education Commission, also referred to as the Radhakrishnan Commission, in 1948.

The government also established a number of commissions and committees for educational reform and adjustments to India's higher education system in the years that followed.

- The Education Commission's Report from 1966–1967
- 1968's National Policy on Education
- Draft Education Policy, 1978
- 1982's National Commission on Teachers II

- Education's Challenge: A Policy Perspective, 1985
- 1986 National Policy for Education
- A Program of Action for National Policy on Education, 1986
- A Perspective Paper on Education from 1960, "Towards an Enlightened and Human Society"
- A Programme of Action for National Education Policy, 1992

The Secondary Education Commission, often known as the Mudaliar Commission, was established by the Indian government on September 23, 1952, with Dr. A.L. Swami Mudalia serving as its chairman. The Commission submitted a 240-page report on August 29, 1953, with 15 chapters. The government established the Secondary Education Commission in 1952 and the University Education Commission in 1948 to advocate for educational changes. The commission emphasized that education should come first in any strategy for fostering national progress.⁷

National Policies on Education

It is impossible to overstate the importance of having a national education policy because it is crucial to a nation's growth. The first national education strategy was created in 1968 with the goal of preparing qualified individuals to take on leadership roles in the various areas of our country's rehabilitation.

The National Education Policy of 1968 underwent some revisions after being in place for 20 years in order to reflect changes in various industries. The Indian government's new education strategy was known as the National Policy on Education in 1986. The National Education Policy under 23 Task Force covered the following topics in order to eliminate disparities and emphasize the steps to equalize educational opportunity for women, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, the handicapped, and certain minority groups who are either educationally deprived or backward;

1. Making the System functional.
2. School education practices and content.

3. Education to Advance Gender Equality
4. Education for the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and other underprivileged groups
5. Education of Minorities
6. Education for Disabled People
7. Adult education and ongoing learning
8. Early Childhood Education and Care
9. Elementary education, includes "Operation Blackboard" and non-formal education
10. Navodaya Vidyalayas and Secondary Education
11. Vocationalisation
12. Academic Profession
13. Open Universities and Online Education
14. Education in Technical and Management
15. Development and Research
16. Media and educational technology, such as computer use in the classroom
17. Disentangling education from employment and workforce planning
18. The Cultural Perspective and Language Policy Implementation
19. Youth, Sports, and Physical Education
20. Exam Reforms and the Evaluation Process
- 21 Management of Education
22. Universities and Institutes in Rural Areas

In 1992, the National Policy in Education (NPE), which was enacted in 1936, was reviewed and its Programme of Action (POA), which was the result of discussions, consultations, and consensus, was updated. An education committee was presided over by the National Front Government, which has been in power at the Center since 1990 and is led by the Sarvodaya leader Prof. Ram Murti. The objective

was to assess outmoded educational methods and offer novel solutions for the nation's industry and rural development.

The Janardan Reddy Committee was established in 1992 to thoroughly examine the Report Prof. Ram Murti presented to the Central Advisory Board of Education in 1990. It was developed to keep track of the educational growth of scheduled caste and indigenous group members in order to advance them to a desirable educational standard in accordance with their innate skills and expressed preferences.⁸

In order to provide the previously neglected backward class people with all the luxuries they require, the Committee placed a major priority on the creation of a unified educational system. The Committee also provided recommendations for adult education, secondary, tertiary, teacher preparation, and financial aid. Instructions on how to provide children with a free, universal education were also offered. Additionally, it suggested the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) be appointed.

Current Scenario of Education in India

Even while the Center also has some educational obligations, the several States of the country are given responsibility for improving education in their specific regions. The 1976 Constitutional Amendment states that the State and the Center now jointly oversee numerous academic subjects. The Center sets standards for higher education, technical education, scientific education, and advanced research.

The Government of India is required to plan, allocate, and distribute the financial resources required for the development of Central Universities in India, according to the University Grants Commission. The two governments receive support from the Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE), which was established to ensure continuous parity in the sphere of higher education.

A number of vocations are covered by the nation's technical education system, including engineering, technology, management, architecture, and medicine. Funding for programs at the undergraduate, graduate, post-graduate, and research levels is

provided by the Ministry of Human Resource Development. Professional councils like the National Council for Teacher Education, All India Council for Technical Education, Distance Education Council, Medical Council of India, and others provide grants and other awards to undergraduate programs in order to promote professional institutions.

The decision to educate the adult illiterate population was a wise one made by our administration. To help adults perform their civic duties as informed citizens in a democracy, adult education has emphasized the development of students' personalities in addition to their reading skills. A program for adult education was introduced in 1973. After completing their secondary school, it is intended to provide rural youngsters with further education so they can aid in the growth of their communities. The program's first version made its premiere in 1956.

The Central Ministry of Education established the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) in 1961 to carry out its educational plans and objectives. The council collaborates with numerous universities and boards of education across the country to expand educational opportunities. Four regional educational institutes, located in Ajmer, Bhopal, Bhubaneswar, and Mysore, are under the control of the Council. Throughout the summer, these universities offer in-service training for teachers and teacher preparation programs.

Now here we have to face the competitive exams in all aspects in government. These exams based on CBSE Syllabus, so CBSE students only more chance of cracking these exams. The state board syllabus is less chance to crack exams. A universal common syllabus would give more chances to equality to work in central and state government. Common Syllabus makes more knowledge in all aspects as well as to solve the better communication in all languages. Especially English speaking also better among students. Every state has followed and add regional language also one or two subjects. In this methods to solve issues to students and teacher.⁸

Challenges and Issues

The following are India's main educational challenges. There are several problems involved in upholding the educational standards in more than a million schools across the country, providing instructors with training opportunities, and maintaining a healthy balance with the global education system. Schools must make compromises in the chances for students' overall development because of the variety in size and resources available to them. Making education available to all facets of society becomes more difficult due to socioeconomic problems and infrastructure limitations.

Even for those who live in accessible locations, the expense of education is extremely high. For instance, the pressure of competition on students and parents leads them to choose private tuition & training as a complement to their formal education.

Social & Cultural

India's ethnic variety makes it difficult to administer consent education across the country. More than 300 languages are used throughout the nation, which makes it challenging to provide instruction that is specialized to a given social section. In certain countries, educating women is a significant problem. Children from low-income homes must labor and lose out on educational chances. Adults who lack literacy have relatively few options to pursue education in later years of their lives.

Education system promotes Rate Race

In essence, our educational system encourages the rat race in our youth. They must read the full text book and memorize it without any comprehension. A student who has a score of 90 out of 100 and places first is still a rat.

Education does not build Persona of a Child

Unfortunately, the development of a child's personality is not supported by our educational system. Always keep in mind that personality is more crucial than academic credentials.

No Critical Analysis, only following the Establishment:

The ability to critically analyze anything, including our history, culture, and religion, is lacking in our youth. They adopt the establishment's position or the opinions of the vast majority. They are unable to see things from their own perspective, plain and simple. Children must be taught to critique their own culture as well as other widely accepted myths.

Too much Localism Rather Global outlook

Too much nationalism is taught in our schools, and this could influence the thinking of the next generation.

Teachers themselves are not trained and Efficient

The fact that our teachers lack the necessary training to teach children just makes the situation worse. They lack the necessary training on how to instill principles in youngsters that will alter the course of the nation's future.

Medium of language of our education system

This is a serious problem as well that need attention. We are unable to choose the language that is utilized in our educational system. English is stressed despite the fact that the majority of children cannot understand it. Then, how will kids be able to understand what the professors are saying? Also, the communication medium has little to do with subjects like math, physics, and the arts. As a result, it would not be wise to place too much emphasis on English.

Education given is irrelevant to job – market

The most evident failure of our educational system may be the difficulty of graduates from any discipline to find employment. It is simply due to the fact that recent graduates lack the skills required by the labor market. Everything a child learns in high school and college is virtually irrelevant for career markets. At schools or other institutions, they do not acquire the necessary skills. Our educational system must be modernized and adjusted to reflect our economic interests as a consequence.

Students happy in getting a highly paid salary job but lacks ambition to become entrepreneur

Our kids' mentality is turning them into the property of a select few multinational corporations. Therefore, rather than preparing students for salaried employment, our educational system ought to focus on preparing them to become successful entrepreneurs.⁹

. Provisions in the Indian Constitution on education

- Article 21A was added as part of the B6th Constitutional Amendment Act of 2002, changing the status of basic education from a Directive Principle to a Fundamental Right.
- Section 45. A change has made early childhood care and education available to children under the age of six.
- The Right to Free and Compulsory Education Act of 2009. In order to implement article 21A, this Act was passed. Additionally, it provided critical legal backing for the execution of the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyam. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan has existed since 2000–2001.

India is renowned for the quality of its educational system, but it has come under fire for failing to give students the employability they need in order to meet business needs. As a result, the Indian education sector is currently dealing with a number of issues that demand rapid attention.

Teacher-to-student ratio: 11.16 lakh teaching positions are still available in schools, according to the UNESCO's State of the education report for India in 2021. It demonstrates unequivocally that there aren't enough teachers in public schools. Teachers frequently have a lot of obligations outside of the classroom, which makes it challenging for them to focus on what they are teaching the kids.

Inadequate cleanliness, a lack of restrooms and drinking water facilities, electricity, playgrounds, etc., are some of the largest infrastructure inadequacies in the education sector. 95.2% of schools, according to a survey conducted in 2010, no

longer meet all of the RTE (RIGHT TO EDUCATION) infrastructural requirements. The 2016 Annual Survey of Education Report states. 3.5% of Indian schools had no restrooms at all, and just 68.7% had working ones.

Regional Languages Were Neglected in 2017–18: Compared to 19.3% of students in urban regions, 14% of private school pupils in India's rural areas preferred to study in English. English is the primary language of instruction. Additionally, there are no standardized publications in Indian languages. Students from rural homes as a result. It may be difficult for students in government schools and those who do not speak English fluently to absorb new material and comprehend concepts.

Inadequate practical knowledge and a curriculum that is out of date. The ancient Indian educational system is no longer largely focused on bookish learning, thanks to the internet and practical learning methods. There have been several changes. The use of the abacus and Vedic mathematics had expanded the scope of the subject of mathematics. More educational options and enjoyable study methods were now available.

Similarly. The primary objective of the previous educational system was to cram in as many theories and ideas as possible. Because both parents and teachers place more of an emphasis on assisting students in achieving good grades in the disciplines than on application and utility of the concept, there is no practical exposure provided to the pupils. As a result, school has turned into a race against time. India presently has three educational policies as a result of the implementation of the National Policy on Education 2020. Three of them have already occurred: the first in 1968, the second in 1986, and the third in 2020. The main educational plan for 2020 is bigger and more inclusive. It strives to give students jobs through education that is skill-based. The New Educational Policy 2020 fills every gap left by the previous educational plans. A child's primary and secondary education should come first. Our production approach must adapt to the kids' inventiveness; it shouldn't be built on cramming.

More funding needs to be allocated by the Indian government for building school infrastructure and training teachers. According to the National Education Policy 2022, the government must take the necessary actions to guarantee that

everyone has access to a high-quality education. Students can choose a language based on their individual interests. Improving the educational system is necessary right away. in accordance with the ASER 2020 study. Children in rural areas make about one-third of those who are entirely illiterate. To ensure that teachers are adequately trained and that the problems impacting primary and secondary education in India are fixed, the government must take decisive action.

India's educational system has faced numerous challenges, but there are also many chances to overcome these challenges and enhance India's educational system. Transparency and accountability are crucial for developing a quality educational system and achieving long-term knowledge-building objectives, making the existence of sincere and committed educational institutions crucial.

The future of education looks as promising as never before .The two years of the pandemic pave the way towards newer possibilities and innovations dimensions in learning. The National Education Policy 2020 has laid down many structural and functional changes and updations are on the cards.

The Education industry stood up with the help of technology and catered to the needs of the children. In the year 2021, many schools could not reach the very remote locations of India due to the lack of basic infrastructure facilities for electricity and internet availability. It got us thinking about reducing the future so that not a single child is left behind. ¹⁰

Suggestions

Encourage creativity and innovation. Those who merit higher academic honor should receive rewards from the system. Our testing methods need to be developed to identify unique contribution originality, problem solution, and invitation; ranks should be granted in accordance. Cramming should not be recognized.

Continuously improve the trainers' skills a teacher is a business owner and an artist. A teacher's duties should extend beyond the classroom. Teaching positions are frequently seen as secure, well-paying, and risk-free careers. Most educators are unwilling to change. As they gain expertise, they grow cynical and fail to consider the

needs and nature of the students. The need is to comprehend the current generation. This direction should be taken without any guidance. The Indian government must make significant investments in infrastructure and teacher training; the education sector must get at least 8–10% of India's GDP.

Conclusion

It is a nation's lifeline; education must be prioritized over defense in every nation. India's educational system desperately needs radical reforms, not just in terms of curriculum and pedagogy but also in terms of students' attitudes about tests and the grading system. Every child has limitless potential, which should be allowed to exist unhindered by our diseases. There should be a lesson on how much we can do to lessen inequity. But we are not taking our work as seriously as we should. At present statically report says 2022, our total literacy rate 77.70 percent .In 2020 India globally Literacy rate 34 th rank. Every person should be in educating the in India. It is most valuable source in every citizen of India.

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